

A novel approach to evaluate the effects of offshore energy infrastructure on the northern Gulf of Mexico shrimp fleet

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Manuscript supplementary materials

TABLES

Table S1. WEA size in kilometers squared and total shrimping effort in hours for 2015 to 2019.

WEA	Area (sqkm)	Total Effort 2015-2019 (hours)
A	276.3	12905.7
B	161.2	2589
C	299.9	2476.4
D	276.2	9500.1
E	207.2	6829.7
F	414.6	6242.7
G	161.2	10811.5
H	161.3	3833.2
I	2212.2	41939
J	2005.5	29347.1
K	484.2	1977.2
L	368.9	1201.6
M	477.6	17640.7
N	230.6	7183

Table S2. Estimated parameters, standard errors, and 95% confidence intervals for the full 1km model presented in eqn (3).

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
(Intercept)	28.61	14.48	0.22	56.99
statzone14	-53.63	17.94	-88.79	-18.48
statzone15	-40.43	17.45	-74.64	-6.23
statzone16	-54.72	22.91	-99.62	-9.83
statzone17	-52.23	15.30	-82.22	-22.23
statzone18	-15.41	27.00	-68.34	37.51
statzone19	20.68	45.45	-68.40	109.76
statzone20	-57.22	50.46	-156.12	41.69
log(tot_sz_eff)	-2.43	1.37	-5.11	0.24
treatmentdes	-0.32	0.17	-0.65	0.00
statzone14:log(tot_sz_eff)	4.76	1.67	1.48	8.04
statzone15:log(tot_sz_eff)	3.56	1.61	0.40	6.72
statzone16:log(tot_sz_eff)	4.80	2.06	0.76	8.84
statzone17:log(tot_sz_eff)	4.63	1.43	1.82	7.44
statzone18:log(tot_sz_eff)	1.35	2.47	-3.51	6.20
statzone19:log(tot_sz_eff)	-1.88	4.13	-9.97	6.20
statzone20:log(tot_sz_eff)	5.17	4.70	-4.04	14.38
statzone14:treatmentdes	0.65	0.30	0.07	1.24
statzone15:treatmentdes	0.44	0.21	0.03	0.85
statzone16:treatmentdes	0.78	0.22	0.35	1.21
statzone17:treatmentdes	0.62	0.20	0.23	1.01
statzone18:treatmentdes	0.66	0.40	-0.13	1.45
statzone19:treatmentdes	0.28	0.43	-0.56	1.11
statzone20:treatmentdes	1.07	0.79	-0.47	2.61
Std.Dev.(Intercept) complex_id	1.31		1.19	1.45

Table S3. Estimated parameters, standard errors, and 95% credible intervals for the full 7.5km model presented in eqn (3).

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
(Intercept)	14.23	8.64	-2.71	31.16
statzone14	-22.08	10.10	-41.87	-2.28
statzone15	-22.50	10.40	-42.88	-2.12
statzone16	-47.09	12.70	-71.97	-22.20
statzone17	-29.16	9.08	-46.95	-11.37
statzone18	-5.80	17.16	-39.45	27.84
statzone19	29.43	27.76	-24.97	83.84
statzone20	0.00	24.76	-48.53	48.53
log(tot_sz_eff)	-0.63	0.81	-2.23	0.96
treatmentdes	-0.38	0.11	-0.60	-0.15
statzone14:log(tot_sz_eff)	1.93	0.94	0.08	3.78
statzone15:log(tot_sz_eff)	1.95	0.96	0.07	3.83
statzone16:log(tot_sz_eff)	4.08	1.15	1.83	6.33
statzone17:log(tot_sz_eff)	2.54	0.85	0.88	4.21
statzone18:log(tot_sz_eff)	0.47	1.57	-2.60	3.55
statzone19:log(tot_sz_eff)	-2.67	2.52	-7.61	2.26
statzone20:log(tot_sz_eff)	-0.11	2.30	-4.62	4.41
statzone14:treatmentdes	0.43	0.17	0.10	0.76
statzone15:treatmentdes	0.33	0.14	0.06	0.60
statzone16:treatmentdes	0.52	0.14	0.25	0.79
statzone17:treatmentdes	0.28	0.13	0.02	0.53
statzone18:treatmentdes	0.30	0.28	-0.25	0.84
statzone19:treatmentdes	-0.09	0.26	-0.60	0.42
statzone20:treatmentdes	-0.18	0.40	-0.96	0.60
Std.Dev.(Intercept) complex_id	0.80		0.72	0.88

Fig S1. Aggregated total shrimping effort in hours per month across the Louisiana-Texas shelf from 2015 to 2019 on an 8x8 km grid. WEAs outlines are also displayed in magenta.

Fig S2. Plots in the left column are annual aggregates of VMS data per StatZone across the Louisiana-Texas shelf from 2015 to 2019. Plots in the right column are annual aggregates of VMS data per Wind Energy Area (WEA) across the Louisiana-Texas shelf from 2015 to 2019. The top row plots are effort in hours, the middle row is the number of vessels, and the bottom row plots are effort per vessel.

Figure S3. As buffer size increases, it takes up an increasing proportion of the StatZone area, as shown on the y-axis. The x-axis shows the proportion of shrimp effort within the buffer area per StatZone. Each point represents a buffer size used in the buffer analysis (e.g., 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 17.5, 20, 25, 30, 40 km). This figure seems to suggest that the amount of effort relative to rigs is a function of the space. For example, the largest buffer size of 40km takes up nearly 80% of StatZone 20, but shrimpers only spend around 20% of their effort in the buffer area. In contrast, StatZone21 has fewer rigs, so only ~30% of the area is encompassed in the buffer area, but more than 40% of the effort takes place in this buffer area.

Figure S4. The proportion of shrimp vessel effort as a function of distance from rig per StatZone. Each plot displays the annual effort summed for each buffer distance.

Fig S5. Shrimping Effort in hours (top row) and proportion of shrimping effort as a function of total shrimping effort per StatZone (bottom row) the year before construction and year after construction with the 7.5 km buffer around each rig constructed. There was only one rig constructed in 2017 and 2018.

Figure S6. Full 1 km model diagnostics using the DHARMA simulate residuals ($n = 10,000$ simulations).

Figure S7. Full 7.5 km model diagnostics using the DHARMA simulate residuals ($n = 10,000$ simulations).